

A STUDY ON ESG AWARENESS AND ITS IMPACT ON THE INVESTMENT PREFERENCES OF WORKING PROFESSIONALS IN MUMBAI DISTRICT

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Abstract

Sustainable investing, guided by Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) principles, has emerged as a crucial aspect of contemporary financial decision-making. While institutional investors have increasingly integrated ESG considerations into their investment strategies, awareness and adoption among individual investors—particularly working professionals—remain relatively limited in India. This descriptive study aims to examine the level of ESG awareness among working professionals in the Mumbai district and to analyze how such awareness influences their investment preferences. Using a structured questionnaire administered through a non-probability convenience sampling method, the study seeks to assess participants' understanding of ESG concepts, their perceptions of ESG investments in terms of profitability, risk, and ethical responsibility, and the extent to which these factors shape their investment behavior. The study also explores the moderating role of demographic characteristics and financial literacy in ESG-based investment decisions. Data will be analyzed using descriptive statistics to identify prevailing trends and patterns in investor attitudes and preferences. The findings are expected to provide valuable insights for policymakers, financial institutions, and asset managers in promoting sustainable investment practices among urban professionals. This research contributes to the growing literature on behavioral finance and sustainable investing by highlighting the determinants influencing ESG-oriented investment preferences among working professionals in Mumbai district.

Key Words: *ESG Awareness, Sustainable Investing, Investment Preferences, Working Professionals, Environmental, Social, and Governance*

1.1. Introduction

Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) investing has increasingly become a cornerstone of sustainable finance worldwide. By integrating ethical, social, and environmental considerations alongside financial returns, ESG investing reflects a growing commitment among investors to foster long-term value that benefits society at large. Despite the global surge in ESG-driven strategies, individual investor awareness and participation in ESG investing have shown significant variation across regions, particularly in emerging economies like India. Mumbai, regarded as the financial capital of India, hosts a large population of working professionals who play a critical role in shaping the country's investment landscape. According to industry reports, the assets under management (AUM) in ESG-themed mutual funds in India surged from approximately ₹2,700 crore in 2019 to about ₹11,000 crore by mid-2025 (Financial Express, 2025). This nearly fourfold increase underscores the rapid expansion and growing investor interest in sustainable investment products, though awareness among individual investors remains underexplored. Recognizing Mumbai's strategic importance, this study specifically examines working professionals to assess their ESG awareness levels and how such awareness influences their investment choices.

Beyond measuring awareness, this research explores perceptions of ESG investment profitability, risk mitigation, and ethical responsibility—factors crucial in shaping positive attitudes toward sustainable investment products. It also investigates how demographic characteristics and financial literacy moderate ESG investment behavior. By focusing on this influential cohort, the study contributes valuable empirical insights for policymakers, financial institutions, and asset managers seeking to promote ESG investing in India's rapidly evolving capital markets. Ultimately, this research aims to enhance understanding of sustainable finance adoption at the individual investor level, supporting broader efforts toward responsible investing and sustainable development.

In recent years, sustainable investing grounded in Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) principles has transformed the global financial landscape. ESG-driven strategies emphasize ethical, socially responsible, and environmentally conscious investment decisions that align profitability with long-term sustainability. While institutional investors have

integrated these practices widely, ESG awareness among individual investors in India—particularly among working professionals—remains at a developing stage.

1.2. Literature Review

Recent studies highlight the growing integration of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) principles into corporate and investment strategies, emphasizing their role in sustainable performance and investor decision-making. Inamdar (2021) noted that strong ESG practices enhance transparency and confidence, while Mahadule (2025) linked ESG integration to financial resilience. Biswas and Dwivedi (2025) found that ESG reporting boosts investor confidence and firm performance, and Deepmala (2022) confirmed ESG's positive impact on the financial performance of Indian companies. Mandal and Mitra (2023) explored investor perceptions in Kolkata, revealing that ESG awareness, rather than demographics, drives investment behavior. Dayanandan et al. (2024) observed that IFRS adoption strengthens ESG disclosure, whereas Friedman et al. (2021) explained how ESG reporting influences investor behavior and market outcomes. Parashar et al. (2024) highlighted social audits' role in improving accountability, while Ray and Hardi (2024) linked ESG disclosures to sustainability indices. Studies by Shrimal et al. (2024), Yadav (2024), and Chaubey et al. (2025) further demonstrated ESG's influence on stock performance and individual investment choices. Collectively, these works reveal a key research gap in understanding ESG awareness and perception among urban working professionals in India—a gap this study addresses by analyzing ESG awareness, perception, and investment behavior among professionals in Mumbai.

1.2.1. Research Gap

While previous studies have extensively examined ESG practices, reporting standards, and their impact on corporate performance or institutional investment, limited research has explored ESG awareness at the individual investor level, particularly among working professionals in India. Most existing literature emphasizes corporate ESG disclosure, sustainability performance, or stock market implications, leaving a gap in understanding how awareness and perception of ESG principles shape investment decisions of urban professionals. This study addresses that gap by focusing specifically on working professionals in the Mumbai district, assessing their awareness, attitudes, and investment preferences related to ESG-based products. By doing so, it contributes to the limited body of empirical research on sustainable investing behavior among individual investors in India and offers insights that can guide

policymakers, educators, and financial institutions in promoting ESG-oriented investment practices.

1.3. Research Objectives

- To assess the level of ESG awareness among working professionals in the Mumbai district.
- To evaluate perceptions regarding the profitability, risk, and ethical dimensions of ESG investments among these professionals.
- To analyze the impact of ESG awareness on the investment choices and preferences of working professionals.
- To provide actionable insights for policymakers, financial institutions, and asset managers to promote ESG-based investing among urban professionals

1.4. Research Methodology

The research methodology for this study involved collecting primary data from a sample of 189 working professionals in Mumbai district using a structured questionnaire. Convenience sampling technique was employed to select respondents who were accessible and willing to participate. The questionnaire's internal consistency and reliability were verified through the application of Cronbach's Alpha. For statistical analysis, correlation tests were conducted to examine the relationship between ESG awareness and investment preferences, thereby establishing both the validity of the instrument and the significance of the study's findings.

1.4.1. Statement of problem

Despite the rapid global adoption of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) principles in investment decision-making, the awareness and understanding of ESG concepts among individual investors in India, particularly working professionals in metropolitan areas like Mumbai, remains limited. This lack of awareness, coupled with varying levels of financial literacy and differing demographic attributes, may be restricting the adoption of sustainable investment practices. Most existing research focuses on institutional investors or ESG implementation at the corporate level, leaving a significant gap in understanding how ESG awareness influences the investment preferences and behavior of urban professionals. Addressing this gap is crucial for promoting responsible investing and aligning individual financial decisions with broader sustainability objectives.

1.4.2. Hypothesis

Null Hypothesis (H₀): ESG awareness among working professionals in Mumbai has no significant impact on their preference for ESG-based investment products.

Alternate Hypothesis (H₁): ESG awareness among working professionals in Mumbai has a significant impact on their preference for ESG-based investment products.

1.4.3. Scope and limitations

- The study focuses on assessing ESG awareness and its impact on the investment preferences of working professionals in the Mumbai district.
- It covers individuals employed across various sectors such as finance, education, information technology, and services.
- The research is limited to the geographical area of Mumbai and may not represent the views of professionals from other regions in India.
- Primary data was collected through a structured questionnaire using a convenience sampling method, which may introduce sampling bias.
- The study primarily examines ESG awareness, perception, and investment behavior without exploring deeper psychological or cultural influences.
- The statistical analysis is limited to descriptive and correlation techniques; advanced models such as regression or SEM were not applied.
- The study reflects perceptions at a particular point in time and may vary with changing market trends or future awareness levels.

1.5. Data analysis and Interpretation

This section presents the analysis and interpretation of data collected for the study. Statistical techniques were applied to assess the reliability of the measurement scales and to test the proposed hypothesis.

1.5.1. Reliability Analysis

The internal consistency of the measurement scales used in this study was evaluated using **Cronbach’s Alpha (α)**. The results are summarized in **Table 1**.

Table no. 1: Reliability Statistics (Cronbach’s Alpha)			
Section	No. of Items	Cronbach’s Alpha (α)	Reliability Interpretation
Financial Literacy	5	0.864	Very Good internal consistency
ESG Awareness	4	0.752	Acceptable internal consistency
Investor Attitude & Perception	6	0.784	Acceptable to Good internal consistency
Investment Preferences & Behaviour	6	0.811	Good internal consistency

Interpretation

Cronbach’s Alpha was computed to assess the internal consistency of the measurement scales used in this study. As shown in Table no.1, the reliability coefficients ranged from 0.752 to 0.864, indicating that all constructs demonstrated acceptable to very good internal consistency (George & Mallery, 2003).

Specifically, the Financial Literacy section achieved a Cronbach’s Alpha of 0.864, signifying very good reliability. The ESG Awareness scale recorded an Alpha of 0.752, which falls within the acceptable range. The Investor Attitude and Perception section had a value of 0.784, indicating acceptable to good consistency, while Investment Preferences and Behaviour achieved 0.811, denoting good internal consistency.

These results confirm that all the scales used in this study are reliable and suitable for further analysis.

1.5.2. Hypothesis Testing

To examine the relationship between ESG awareness and investment preferences, **correlation analysis** was performed.

- Null Hypothesis (H₀): ESG awareness among working professionals in Mumbai has no significant impact on their preference for ESG-based investment products.
- Alternate Hypothesis (H₁): ESG awareness among working professionals in Mumbai has a significant impact on their preference for ESG-based investment products.

Table: Correlation Results between ESG Awareness and ESG-based Investment Preferences		
Parameter	Value	Interpretation
Correlation Coefficient (r)	0.357	Moderate positive relationship
Sample Size (n)	189	Adequate for correlation analysis
t-value	5.236	Greater than critical t (1.97)
p-value	< 0.001	Statistically significant
Decision	Reject H ₀	Significant relationship exists

Interpretation

The correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between ESG awareness and preference for ESG-based investment products among working professionals in Mumbai. The results revealed a correlation coefficient (r) of 0.357, indicating a moderate positive relationship between ESG awareness and ESG investment preferences. This suggests that as

individuals' awareness of ESG factors increases, their preference for ESG-based investment options tends to rise moderately.

With a t-value of 5.236, which exceeds the critical value of 1.97, and a p-value less than 0.001, the relationship was found to be statistically significant at the 0.05 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_0) that is ESG awareness has no significant impact on ESG investment preference is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is accepted.

This indicates that ESG awareness among working professionals in Mumbai significantly influences their preference toward ESG-based investment products.

1.6. Conclusion

This study set out to examine the level of ESG awareness among working professionals in the Mumbai district and its impact on investment preferences, addressing a significant research gap in the Indian individual investor context. The findings clearly demonstrate that greater awareness of ESG principles is moderately and significantly associated with a preference for ESG-based investment products ($r = 0.357$, $p < 0.001$), substantiating the positive relationship between sustainable investing knowledge and investment choices. This supports the hypothesis that enhanced ESG awareness can meaningfully influence how urban professionals in India allocate their investments, moving beyond purely financial considerations to incorporate ethical and sustainability priorities.

The reliability of the measurement instruments, confirmed through strong Cronbach's Alpha values, ensures that these results are robust and suitable for informing future research and policy interventions. The data highlight that perceptions surrounding profitability, risk management, and ethical responsibility play crucial roles in shaping positive attitudes towards ESG investments among Mumbai's working professionals. At the same time, demographic factors and financial literacy are important contextual variables that deserve further exploration in larger and more diverse samples.

These insights offer actionable directions for policymakers, financial institutions, and asset managers seeking to promote ESG-based investment practices. Efforts to improve ESG education, disclosure, and accessibility will be critical for deepening individual investor engagement with sustainability goals. Continued research should expand to additional regions and longitudinal designs to capture evolving attitudes and market trends in the face of rapid change within India's investment landscape. In summary, raising ESG awareness and fostering responsible investment behaviors among urban professionals can serve as a catalyst for broader

sustainable development, helping to align individual financial decisions with national and global sustainability objectives.

1.7. Suggestion and Recommendation

- Greater efforts should be made to increase awareness of ESG principles among working professionals through training, workshops, and awareness campaigns.
- ESG concepts should be integrated into financial literacy and investment education programs to promote responsible decision-making.
- Companies should improve transparency in reporting their ESG activities to help investors make informed investment choices.
- Financial institutions should develop and promote more ESG-focused investment products to cater to the growing interest in sustainable investing.
- Government and regulatory bodies should provide supportive policies and incentives to encourage sustainable investment practices.
- Future research can be conducted in other regions and professions to gain a wider understanding of ESG awareness and its impact on investment behavior.

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